

Customer Centered Canteen ordering and Management System for UTAS

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Abstract:

Our proposed system is customer centered canteen ordering and management system for UTAS. It enables students and teachers to order food easily. Beat on disadvantages of the traditional queuing system. Our proposed system is a way to order food online without needing to wait the service. The Online food ordering system prepares online food menu and customers can easily place the order as they wish. Also Through the food menu, customers can easily keep track of orders. The system also provides a feedback system by which the user can rate food items and make suggestions about dishes, improvements and complaints. Also, the proposed system can recommend based on the ratings given by the user, canteen staff will be informed for the improvements along with the quality. The payment will be pay-on-delivery System. For more secured ordering separate accounts are maintained for each user by providing them an ID and a password. Our proposed system acts as a link between customers (students and dependents) and the university canteen. When the client opens the site, he is required to enter the ID and a password, which are kept confidentially in the database, when a customer enters the main page of the site, they will find the suggested menu for that day, by clicking on the meal to be selected, the customer can choose the quantity and type – (chicken, meat) - and drinks and the time to take the order. Once the customer has finished ordering the food, he can confirm the order and keep track the status of the food. The status is like preparing and finished with expected time. Once the status is finished, the customer can come and collect the order and payment upon receipt. In our project, the customer can make suggestions and improvements to the canteen and evaluate the food. We chose this project to speed up the procurement process in the university canteen, reduce delays in submitting applications, and reduce long queues and overcrowding in the canteen.